

Research paper

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Effect of supramolecular complex ivermectin 2% ivermectin in increased doses on horses

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Annotation

The aim of the research was to study the effect of supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% ivermectin in increased doses on the clinical condition of horses.

Materials and Methods. The experiment was conducted in October 2020 in the North Caucasus Federal District of the Chechen Republic in the equestrian complex "Seradin" on 20 horses of different breeds. Horses were divided according to the principle of analogies into 3 experimental and one control group of 5 animals each. Horses of the 1st group were administered supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2% in the therapeutic dose of 0.2 mg/kg, the 2nd group - in three times increased dose of 0.6 mg/kg and the 3rd group - in 5 times increased dose of 1.0 mg/kg of DV. The drug was given once individually in a mixture with compound feed. Body temperature was measured with a non-contact thermometer, pulse rate and number of respiratory movements per 1 min. Urine of horses was examined on the 1st, 7th and 14th day after the drug administration. The color, transparency and consistency of urine were determined. Universal indicator paper was used to study pH, protein, glucose, ketone bodies, nitrites, bilirubin, urobilinogen. Blood was taken in the morning from the jugular vein of horses on the 1st, 7th and 14th day after the drug administration. Studies of hematological and biochemical parameters were performed on analyzers.

Results and Discussion. Clinical signs of horses (body temperature, pulse and respiration) after administration of supramolecular complex ivermectin 2.0% in therapeutic, 3 and 5 times increased doses on the 1st, 7th and 14th days did not differ from the indicators of animals of the control group. A slight increase of ketone bodies was noted in urine on the 1st day, which may indicate the effect of the drug in 5 times increased dose on the central nervous system; on the 7th and 14th days all parameters were within the normal range. Supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% in increased doses (0.6; 1.0 mg/kg DV) had no negative effect on hematological and biochemical blood parameters of horses.

Keywords: supramolecular complex, ivermectin, clinical condition, hematology, biochemistry, horses

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No conflict of interest

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Original article

Effects of the 2% supramolecular complex of ivermectin in overdoses on horses

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Abstract

The purpose of the research is to study effects of the 2.0% supramolecular complex of ivermectin in overdoses on the clinical condition of horses.

Materials and methods. The experiment was conducted on 20 horses of different breeds in the Seradin Equestrian Center, the North Caucasus Federal District, the Chechen Republic, in October 2020. The horses were divided according to the principle of analogues into 3 test groups and one control group of 5 animals each. The 2.0% supramolecular complex of ivermectin was administered to the horses from group 1 at a therapeutic dose of 0.2 mg/kg; group 2 received a tripled dose of 0.6 mg/kg, and the group 3, a 5-fold increased dose of 1.0 mg/kg for the active substance. The drug was administered once individually in a mixture with compound feed. The body temperature was measured with a non-contact thermometer, and the pulse rate and the respiratory rate were measured per 1 min. Urine of the horses was examined on days 1, 7 and 14 after the drug. The urine color, transparency and consistency were determined. Multifunctional test paper was used to study pH, protein, glucose, ketone bodies, nitrites, bilirubin, and urobilinogen. Blood was taken in the morning from the horses' jugular vein on days 1, 7 and 14 after the drug. Hematological and biochemical parameters were studied on analyzers.

Results and discussion. Clinical findings of the horses (body temperature, pulse and respiration) did not differ from those of the control animals after the 2.0% supramolecular complex of ivermectin was administered in a therapeutic, tripled and 5-fold increased doses on days 1, 7 and 14. A slight increase in ketone bodies was observed in the urine on day 1, which may indicate the drug effect on the central nervous system at a 5-fold increased dose; all parameters were within the normal range on days 7 and 14. The 2.0% supramolecular complex of ivermectin in overdoses (0.6; 1.0 mg/kg for the active substance) did not adversely affect the horses' hematological or biochemical blood parameters.

Keywords: supramolecular complex, ivermectin, clinical condition, hematology, biochemistry, horses

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There is no conflict of interests

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Introduction

In horses, the most widespread nematodes of the digestive tract are parascaris, trichonematids, oxiurids, strongylates - larval stages of which cause severe diseases such as. alfortiosis, delafondiasis and strongylosis with fatal outcome, causing great economic damage to horse breeding [3].

Preparations from the group of macrocyclic lactones (ivermectins), which have a broad spectrum of action and are highly active against endo- and ectoparasites in small doses, are often used in the control of parasitic diseases of animals [1].

We have developed a paste based on ivermectin - Equiverm-2.0%, which showed high antiparasitic and economic efficiency in deworming horses [9].

Practice has shown that deworming of non-tame animals with preparations in the form of injections and pastes is problematic. Therefore, we developed a 2.0% antiparasitic supramolecular complex preparation based on ivermectin substance and two water-soluble polymers (arabinogalactan and low-molecular polyvinylpyrrolidone) in the form of finely dispersed powder using nanotechnology for deworming of free-ranging animals [2].

Supramolecular complex of ivermectin showed high activity in gel-mintosis of the digestive tract of horses at the therapeutic dose of 0.2 mg/kg and convenience in application; labor intensity of work is reduced, stress and traumatization of animals and operators during deworming are excluded. Inclusion of arabinogalactan, which is an immunomodulator and has antimutagenic, mitogenic, hepatoprotective, gastroprotective activity, providing targeted delivery of the drug and leveling toxicity, expanding the spectrum of action on tissue helminths and larvae and interaction at the level of excretion [9-11].

Preclinical testing of the drug showed that the parameters of acute oral and dermal toxicity of supramo-

lecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% belongs to the 4th class in contrast to the substance of the 3rd class of hazard. The drug has weakly expressed cumulative properties ($K_{\text{квм}} = 6,05$). In the absence of local irritant action, when applied to the skin of rats and after intraconjunctival injection of the drug, a moderate irritant effect on the conjunctiva, estimated at 1 point, was noted [4-7]. The supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% showed no immuno-toxic properties [8].

The aim of our research was to study the effect of supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% ivermectin in increased doses on the clinical condition of horses.

Materials and methods

The study of the effect of supramolecular complex ivermectin on horses was conducted in October 2020 in the North Caucasian Federal District of the Chechen Republic in the equestrian complex "Sera-din" on 20 horses of different breeds: Don, Kabardinian, Russian trotter, English thoroughbred and mixed breeds. Horses were divided according to the principle of analogs into 3 experimental and one control group of 5 animals in each. Horses of the 1st group were administered supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2% in the therapeutic dose of 0.2 mg/kg, the 2nd group - in three times increased dose of 0.6 mg/kg and the 3rd group - in 5 times increased dose of 1.0 mg/kg by DV. The drug was given once individually in a mixture with compound feed. The fourth group of animals did not receive the drug and served as a control. Animals were kept in stalls during the day and grazed in the evening.

Study of clinical condition. After application of supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% in experimental horses, body temperature was determined with a non-contact thermometer, pulse rate and number of respiratory movements per 1 minute.

Study of general urine analysis. On the 1st, 7th and 14th day after the drug administration, urine for the study was collected in the morning in special glasses with visual determination of color, transparency and consistency. Universal indicator paper was used to study pH, protein, glucose, ketone bodies, nitrites, bilirubin, urobilinogen.

Study of hematological and biochemical indices of blood of horses. Blood was taken in the morning from the jugular vein of horses on the 1st, 7th and 14th days of the experiment and studied in the Complex Research Institute named after Kh. I. Ibragimov RAS, using analyzers "Hematoscreen" (Italy) and "Klima MS" (Spain).

Results and discussion

Clinical signs of horses (body temperature, pulse and respiration) after administration of supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% in therapeutic, 3 and 5 times increased doses on the 1st, 7th and 14th days did not differ from the indicators of animals of the control group (Table 1).

Table 1 [Table 1]

Indices of clinical condition of horses after administration of supramolecular complex ivermectin 2.0% ivermectin in increased doses

[Indicators of the clinical condition of horses after the introduction of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% in high doses]

Indicator [Indicator]	Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS [Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS]	The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug [The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug]			Control [Control]
		1	7	14	
Temperature, °C [Temperature, °C]	0,2	37,70±7,54	37,76±7,55	37,80±7,56	37,75±7,55
	0,6	37,72±7,54	37,74±7,55	37,86±7,57	38,00±7,60
	1,0	37,80±7,56	37,66±7,53	37,92±7,58	37,79±7,56
Pulse, beats per 1 min. [Pulse, beats per 1 min.]	0,2	33,7±3,2	32,4±3,1	34,2±3,2	37,0±3,8
	0,6	32,2±3,4	36,0±3,4	29,4±2,6	38,2±3,2
	1,0	34,2±3,8	35,3±3,2	30,0±3,0	27,8±2,4
Breathing, breathing movements 1 minute. [Breath, breath. movement in 1 min.]	0,2	12,0±1,1	12,8±1,5	11,3±1,1	12,0±1,0
	0,6	11,0±1,2	11,2±1,1	10,8±1,0	11,8±1,2
	1,0	10,0±0,4	11,6±1,3	10,2±1,0	11,2±1,1

When analyzing the urine of horses, there was a slight increase in ketone bodies on the 1st day (up to 5/52) in contrast to control lives

This may indicate the effect of the drug at a 5-fold higher dose on the central nervous system (Table 2).

Table 2 [Table 2]

Urine parameters of horses after giving the supramolecular complex

Indicator [Indicator]	Dose, mg/kg, by DV [Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS]	The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug [The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug]			Control [Control]
		1	7	14	
1	2	3	4	5	6
Specific gravity, g/l [Specific gravity, g/l]	0,2	1,030	1,030	1,030	1,030
	0,6	1,030			
	1,0	1,034			
pH	0,2	8,0	0,80	0,80	0,80
	0,6	8,0			
	1,0	7,0			
Protein, g/l [Protein, g/l]	0,2	-	-	-	-
	0,6	-			
	1,0	-			
Glucose, mmol/l [Glucose, mmol/l]	0,2	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
	0,6	Traces			
	1,0	Traces			
Ketone bodies, mmol/l [Ketone bodies, mmol/l]	0,2	1,5/16	1,5/16	1,5/16	1,5/16
	0,6	1,5/16			
	1,0	5/52			
Nitrites, mg/g [Nitrites, mg/g]	0,2	Pos.	Pos.	Pos.	Pos.
	0,6	Pos.			
	1,0	Pos.			

End of table 2 [End of table 2]

Indicator [Indicator]	Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS [Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS]	The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug [The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug]			Control [Control]
		1	7	14	
1	2	3	4	5	6
Bilirubin, mmol/l [Bilirubin, mmol/l]	0,2 0,6 1,0	- + Traces	- + Traces	- + Traces	- + Traces
Urobilinogen, mmol/L [Urobilinogen, mmol/l]	0,2 0,6 1,0	Normal Normal Normal	Normal Normal Normal	Normal Normal Normal	Normal Normal Normal
Blood.	0,2 0,6 1,0	-- - -	-- - -	-- - -	-- - -

(test strips (nona PHAN SG))

Supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% in increased doses has no negative effect on hematological parameters: they are within the normal range (Table 3).

The results of studying the effect of supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% on biochemical parameters of blood of horses in increased doses are summarized in Table 4. It was found that the drug in 5 times increased dose of 1.0 mg/kg on the first day showed a slight increase in total protein (90.2 g/l), albumin (8.0 g/l) and alkaline phosphatase (403.0 U/l). These indices on the 7th and 14th days were within the normal range (87.6-73.2 g/l, 7.1-7.3 g/l, 390.7-388.0 U/l, respectively), i.e. the drug in increased doses does not adversely affect the biochemical parameters of blood of horses.

Conclusion

Clinical signs of horses (body temperature, pulse and respiration) after administration of supramolecular complex ivermectin 2.0% in therapeutic, 3 and 5 times increased doses on the 1st, 7th and 14th days did not differ from the indicators of animals of the control group. A slight increase of ketone bodies in the urine on the 1st day was noted, which may indicate the effect of the drug in 5 times increased dose on the central nervous system; on the 7th and 14th days all parameters were within the normal range. Supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% in increased doses (0.6; 1.0 mg/kg DV) had no negative effect on hematological and biochemical blood parameters of horses.

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Table 3 [Table 3]

**Hematological parameters of horses after the introduction of the
supramolecular complex of**

Indicator [Indicator]		Unit of measurement [Unit of measurement]	The value of the indicator after giving the drug in doses according to AS (mg/kg) [The value of the indicator after giving the drug in doses according to AS (mg/kg)]			Control [Control]
			0,2	0,6	1,0	
1		2	3	4	5	6
<i>Twenty-four hours after giving the drug</i>						
Erythrocytes		x 10 /L ¹²	8,6±0,84	9,2±0,99	8,9±0,87	9,7±0,62
Leukocytes		x 10 /L ⁹	8,43±0,31	8,94±0,24	9,04±0,22	9,16±0,36
Hemoglobin		g/l	139,0±3,12	144,5±2,34	142,0±3,07	148,0±2,65
Leukogram	Basophils	%	0,14±0,02	0,11 ±0,04	0,15±0,02	0,11 ±0,04
	Eosinophils	%	2,58±0,63	3,01 ±0,39	3,65±0,42	3,01±0,51
	Segmented neutrophils	%	53,14±0,91	53,09±0,84	52,5±1,18	52,89±1,01
	Neutrophils are bacilliform.	%	4,26±0,37	3,27±0,31	3,98±0,24	3,89±0,23
	Lymphocytes	%	35,67± 1,92	37,15±1,76	37,38±1,39	36,50±1,43
	Monocytes	%	3,6±0,44	3,4±0,32	2,50±0,29	3,3±0,39
<i>7th day after drug administration</i>						
Erythrocytes		x 10 /L ¹²	7,21 ±0,73	7,5 ±0,65	8,7±0,61	8,9±0,56
Leukocytes		x 10 /L ⁹	9,8±0,86	9,7±0,91	8,3 ±0,75	9,12±0,79
Hemoglobin		g/l	146,0±4,01	144,0±3,46	142,0±3,61	151,0±2,12
Leukogram	Basophils	%	0,14±0,02	0,11 ±0,04	0,15±0,02	0,11 ±0,04
	Eosinophils	%	2,58±0,63	3,01 ±0,39	3,65±0,42	3,01±0,51
	Segmented neutrophils	%	53,14±0,91	53,09±0,84	52,5±1,18	52,89±1,01
	Neutrophils are bacilliform.	%	4,26±0,37	3,27±0,31	3,98±0,24	3,89±0,23
	Lymphocytes	%	36,8± 1,43	37,20±1,49	36,51±1,52	36,78±1,71
	Monocytes	%	3,08±0,44	3,32±0,35	3,21±0,39	3,32±0,41
<i>14th day after drug administration</i>						
Erythrocytes		x 10 /L ¹²	8,91 ±0,85	8,56±0,91	9,25 ±0,63	10,6±0,54
Leukocytes		x 10 /L ⁹	9,2±0,59	8,6±0,70	9,3 ±0,83	9,5±0,75
Hemoglobin		g/l	155,0±3,73	149,0±3,98	151,0±4,32	159,0±3,65

End of table 3 [End of table 3]

Indicator [Indicator]	Unit of measurement [Unit of measurement]	The value of the indicator after giving the drug in doses according to AS (mg/kg) [The value of the indicator after giving the drug in doses according to AS (mg/kg)]			Control [Control]	
		0,2	0,6	1,0		
1	2	3	4	5	6	
Leukogram	Basophils	%	0	0	0,1	0,1
	Eosinophils	%	3,17±0,63	3,41 ±0,59	2,76±0,65	2,7±0,59
	Segmented neutrophils	%	59,67±1,01	57,8±1,13	61,79±0,82	60,4±0,89
	Neutrophils are bacilliform.	%	3,01 ±0,76	3,35±0,58	2,36±0,84	2,04±0,91
	Lymphocytes	%	31,12±1,54	31,75±1,47	30,09±1,69	31,56±1,29
	Monocytes	%	3,03±0,49	3,69±0,52	2,9±0,65	3,2±0,44

Table 4 [Table 4]

**The influence of the supramolecular complex
of ivermectin 2.**

Indicator [Indicator]	Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS [Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS]	The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug [The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug]			Control [Control]
		1	7	14	
ACT, U/L	0,2	374,2±17,6	372,6±17,4	372,4±17,2	372,2± 17,6
	0,6	384,2±22,4	382,4±22,0	376,8±17,0	
	1,0	414,4±26,4	390,2±25,7	380,0±18,0	
ALT, U/L	0,2	28,4±3,2	28,2±2,6	27,8±2,5	26,2±3,2
	0,6	29,8±2,9	29,2±2,8	28,4±2,9	
	1,0	32,2±3,0	30,0±2,9	29,6±2,7	
Alkaline phosphatase, U/L	0,2	342,6±39,1	342,2±32,2	340,4±34,0	340,0±26,2
	0,6	390,6±9,1	390,2±34,0	383,1±36,2	
	1,0	403,0±28,2*	390,7±34,4	388,0±38,4	
Creatinine kinase, U/L	0,2	121,2±10,2	120,8±11,8	120,5±12,1	120,2±10,2
	0,6	127,1±12,7	126,7±12,5	125,8±12,3	
	1,0	130,4±12,8	129,2±12,7	130,2±12,4	
Cholesterol, mmol/L	0,2	2,5±0,3	2,5 ±0,4	2,4±0,2	2,5±0,3
	0,6	2,6±0,3	2,5 ±0,4	2,4±0,2	
	1,0	2,6±0,3	2,6±0,5	2,5±0,3	
Triglycerides, mg%	0,2	0,1 ±0,9	0,1 ±0,6	0,1 ±0,6	0,1 ±0,9
	0,6	9,5±0,9	9,7±0,5	0,1 ±0,6	
	1,0	9,4±0,8	9,5 ±0,3	9,7±0,5	

End of table 4 [End of table 4]

Effect of supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0% on blood biochemical parameters of horses**[The influence of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin 2.0 % on the biochemical parameters of the blood of horses.]**

Indicator [Indicator]	Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS [Dose, mg/kg, according to the AS]	The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug [The value of the indicator, days after giving the drug]			Control [Control]
		1	7	14	
Bilirubin, $\mu\text{mol/L}$	0,2	10.4 $\pm$ 1,1	10,5 $\pm$ 0,9	10,6 $\pm$ 1,2	10.6 $\pm$ 1,1
	0,6	12.0 $\pm$ 1,1	11,8 $\pm$ 1,2	10,8 $\pm$ 1,3	
	1,0	12,4 $\pm$ 1,1	12.0 $\pm$ 1,1	10,9 $\pm$ 1,3	
Urea, mmol/L	0,2	5,2 $\pm$ 0,5	5,3 $\pm$ 0,5	5,4 $\pm$ 0,3	5,4 $\pm$ 0,5
	0,6	5,5 $\pm$ 0,5	5,5 $\pm$ 0,6	5,4 $\pm$ 0,3	
	1,0	5,6 $\pm$ 0,6	5,5 $\pm$ 0,6	5,4 $\pm$ 0,4	
Glucose, mmol/L	0,2	4,4 $\pm$ 0,4	4,5 $\pm$ 0,4	4,7 $\pm$ 0,5	4,8 $\pm$ 0,5
	0,6	4,5 $\pm$ 0,4	4,6 $\pm$ 0,5	4,8 $\pm$ 0,5	
	1,0	4,6 $\pm$ 0,5	4,7 $\pm$ 0,5	4,8 $\pm$ 0,5	
Urokinase, mol/L	0,2	76,0 $\pm$ 6,9	76,2 $\pm$ 7,4	76,6 $\pm$ 7,2	76,6 $\pm$ 6,8
	0,6	75,7 $\pm$ 7,6	75,9 $\pm$ 7,6	76,2 $\pm$ 7,1	
	1,0	74,2 $\pm$ 7,4	75,3 $\pm$ 7,3	76,0 $\pm$ 7,2	
Iron, $\mu\text{mol/L}$	0,2	17,6 $\pm$ 1,8	17,9 $\pm$ 1,7	18,0 $\pm$ 1,7	18,0 $\pm$ 1,7
	0,6	17,4 $\pm$ 1,7	17,4 $\pm$ 1,6	17,8 $\pm$ 1,6	
	1,0	17,2 $\pm$ 1,6	17,4 $\pm$ 1,6	17,7 $\pm$ 1,6	
Total protein, g/l	0,2	60,6 $\pm$ 6,1	60,7 $\pm$ 6,1	60,8 $\pm$ 6,1	60,8 $\pm$ 6,1
	0,6	82,0 $\pm$ 8,0	81,5 $\pm$ 8,2	72,7 $\pm$ 7,3	
	1,0	90,2 $\pm$ 8,8	87,6 $\pm$ 7,9	73,2 $\pm$ 7,1	
Albumin, g/l	0,2	7,2 $\pm$ 0,6	7,2 $\pm$ 0,7	7,3 $\pm$ 0,6	7,4 $\pm$ 0,6
	0,6	7,6 $\pm$ 0,7	7,3 $\pm$ 0,7	7,4 $\pm$ 0,6	
	1,0	8,0 $\pm$ 0,7	7,1 $\pm$ 0,6	7,3 $\pm$ 0,6	

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